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CONTACTS

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AGGREGATE FACTORS OF ENSURING REGIONAL ECONOMIC SECURITY AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION

Nurxonov Komiljon Tovkarayevich

Independent Researcher

Karshi State Technical University

ORCID: 0009-0001-7839-2417

Email: komilnurxonov1986@gmail.com

Abstract: The article analyzes the general factors ensuring the economic security of a region, as well as the conditions shaping them, and proposes their classification into macro- and meso-level factors.

Keywords: economic security, region, competitiveness, micro-level, macro-level, meso-level, conditions, technological, organizational and managerial, legal, socio-cultural factors.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada mintaqaning iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlashning yalpi omillari, ularni shakllantiruvchi shart-sharoitlar tahlil etilgan hamda ularning makrodarajadagi va mezodaraja omillari tasnifi tavsiya etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy xavfsizlik, mintaqa, raqobatbardoshlik, mikrodaraja, makrodaraja, mezodaraja, shart-sharoitlar, texnologik, tashkiliy-boshqaruv, huquqiy, ijtimoiy-madaniy omillar.

Аннотация: В статье проанализированы общие факторы обеспечения экономической безопасности региона и условия их формирования, а также предложена их классификация на макро- и мезоуровневые факторы.

Ключевые слова: экономическая безопасность, регион, конкурентоспособность, микроуровень, макроуровень, мезоуровень, условия, технологические, организационно-управленческие, правовые, социально-культурные факторы.

INTRODUCTION

The consistent reduction of existing disparities among the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in terms of digitalization, social development, resource availability, and infrastructure expansion creates broader opportunities to further strengthen the country's territorial integrity and its economic security. Taking into account the responsibility and accountability of regions in ensuring their own economic security, particular attention is being paid to studying the factors that ensure regional economic security, including high adaptive mobility and the protection of economic interests.

In our country, the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 provides for ensuring economic security in the national economy and its regions, as well as for developing and improving the scientific foundations of its key factors. "The economic situation in the global market has become more complex, and the nature of economic relations between countries has fundamentally changed. Economic competition has intensified significantly, becoming increasingly sharp and uncompromising. In such conditions, it is of critical importance to introduce mechanisms that ensure the continuous improvement of our national economy and to clearly define the tasks related to sustainable economic development" [1].

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Among foreign scholars who have studied the theoretical aspects of regional socio-economic development, as well as the factors ensuring the economic security of countries and their regions, it is possible to mention B.G. Kleiner, G.A. Simon, G. Haken, W.B. Arthur, R. Myerson, E. Maskin, J.A. Schumpeter, A. Kuhlmann, and C.E. Shannon.

Among Russian scholars, M.Ya. Kornilov, V.V. Krivorotov, S.E. Lelyukhina, G.E. Lyagusheva, E.S. Mityakova, S.A. Makin, V.K. Senchagov, A.I. Tatarkin, D.V. Tretyakov and others have conducted scientific research on this topic.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan and its regions, the scientific-theoretical and regional aspects of ensuring

economic security under conditions of external and internal threats have been studied by national scholars such as Abulqosimov X.P., Mamatov A.A., Nazarov Sh.X., Axmedov T.M., Ergashev R.X., Xamrayeva S.N., Xurramov A.F., Tursunov B.O., and others.

The concept of “economic security” was initially recognized and institutionally formalized at the level of state organizations, as for a long time the state was considered the sole holder of sovereign rights. In June 1934, U.S. President Franklin D. Roosevelt established the world’s first “Committee on Economic Security” [2]. From the perspective of classifying economic mechanisms proposed by A. Kuhlmann based on their influence on economic phenomena and processes, it is possible to distinguish between open and closed types of mechanisms [3].

Russian scholar V.K. Senchagov developed a classification of factors based on their spheres of influence, distinguishing between external and internal factors of the region at macro- and meso-economic levels. According to the scholar, such classification is carried out, on the one hand, on a regional basis, that is, by levels of the country, and on the other hand, by types of sectoral activities of socio-economic entities [4]. S.A. Makin emphasizes that if we take the generally accepted division of factors into external and internal ones, and add the criterion of their objective emergence and the nature of their impact on economic security, we obtain a multifactor model that determines the level of regional economic security [5].

Among Uzbek economists, Professor Abulqosimov X.P. defines regional security as the protection of the interests of the country’s regions from internal and external threats. According to him, regional security includes natural-technogenic, food, general economic, socio-political, and social security factors [6]. Professor Tursunov B.O. defines economic security as a set of conditions and factors that ensure the independence of the national economy, its stability, resilience, and its ability for continuous renewal and self-improvement [7].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article employs dialectical, systemic, integral, and synergetic approaches, as well as economic and logical methods, scientific abstraction, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, comparison, generalization, grouping, and tabular methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The socio-economic system of a region consists of a set of elements and the interrelations between them. The main driving force of economic development is the contradiction of interests among various economic entities, arising from the interaction of random factors. The relevance of ensuring economic security at the regional level determines the need to study the “architecture” of the main factors affecting the security of the region’s socio-economic system and to systematize them according to specific criteria.

Regional threats are defined as a set of real and potential internal and external threats, or conditions and risk factors that may cause a certain degree of damage to society in the sphere of economic activity. Since threats arise due to the continuous development of internal and external processes under conditions of increasing instability, responses to them should be aimed at ensuring a certain level of protection of the regional economy and its internal and external environment.

Ensuring economic security at the regional level largely depends on the study of general internal and external factors, as the impact of each factor affects different elements of the economic security system to varying degrees. Therefore, it is considered appropriate to identify and systematize the aggregate factors influencing economic security at the regional level. Within the framework of this research, these factors are understood as the driving forces that objectively influence the process of ensuring or increasing the level of economic security of the regional economic system.

It is necessary to distinguish between the factors and the conditions for ensuring economic security in a region. While factors are mainly objective in nature, conditions are related circumstances that change as a result of ensuring and improving the level of economic security. If factors represent objective determinants of economic security, then appropriate conditions must be created to ensure the continuous protection of the regional system from internal and external threats. In order to increase the level of economic security in a region and create the necessary conditions, it is essential to identify and systematize economic security factors.

In our view, the factors currently in operation serve as a basis for forming favorable conditions for enhancing the level of regional economic security in the future. Such conditions include the concentration of resources in priority areas of regional policy such as industry, food security, human resources, energy, innovation, social development, and ecology; the acquisition of additional skills and authority by personnel responsible for ensuring economic security; the formation of an appropriate information and communication environment; and the creation of databases, among others. Thus, factors may evolve into the necessary conditions for

successfully addressing the problem of improving economic security in the future.

In economic literature, classifications of economic security factors are often presented according to various criteria; however, attempts to form a structural framework distinguishing between factors and conditions for ensuring economic security are relatively rare. Some researchers suggest classifying economic security factors based on criteria such as controllability, priority, instruments of influence, evaluation, and localization. Other researchers classify these factors according to their duration (long-term, short-term), level of manifestation (local, regional, national), and other characteristics [8].

The development of a generally accepted and systematized approach to presenting internal and external factors affecting regional economic security would expand the possibilities for creating and applying effective instruments and mechanisms to enhance the level of economic security. The classification of economic security factors proposed in this article provides a basis for incorporating them into strategies and programs aimed at improving the economic security of regional entities, forming favorable conditions for its implementation, and ensuring more rational use of resources allocated for this purpose.

The classification of factors by spheres of influence is proposed in a scientific monograph edited by V.K. Senchagov. In this framework, the external and internal factors of a region are expressed at macro- and meso-economic levels. On the one hand, the classification is carried out on a regional basis, that is, by levels of the country; on the other hand, it is based on the sectoral activities of socio-economic entities [9].

This article proposes a multi-criteria classification of economic security factors, presenting a structure that allows for the systematization of selected factors at each level. In our opinion, it is necessary to substantiate and create the conditions required to increase the level of economic security in a region, as well as to take into account risks and constraints in the development of a regional economic security strategy (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Comprehensive factors ensuring the economic security of the region¹

It is proposed to classify the factors influencing the level of regional economic security according to the following criteria:

By levels of governance:

- economic security factors operating at the micro level;
- economic security factors operating at the meso level;
- economic security factors formed and manifested at the macro level;

By system-forming elements of the regional system (as a system):

- resource-based factors;
- process-based factors;
- result-oriented factors;

In relation to the socio-economic environment of the region:

- internal environment factors;
- external environment factors;

By the nature of their impact on economic security objects in the region:

¹ Source: compiled by the author.

- factors that contribute to increasing the level of economic security in the region (stimulating);
- factors that hinder the improvement of the level of economic security.

The region, as a socio-economic system, represents the meso level of the economy. At the same time, its level of economic security is influenced by a number of factors at the macro, meso, and micro levels. Micro-level factors are conditions that determine the level of economic security of economic entities operating within the region. In classifying meso-level factors, as noted above, various criteria can be used, including the characteristic of the “composition of system-forming elements” applied in this study (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Meso-level factors of economic security grouped by the criterion of “regional system elements” [10]²

A set of meso-level economic security factors is presented, structured according to the composition and content of system-forming elements (inputs, process elements, outputs). The territorial and economic complex of a region represents a subsystem of the national economic system, characterized by significant differences, including diversity in levels of socio-economic development, specific territorial features, the variety of natural resources, the quality of human capital, and other factors. All these elements serve as a methodological basis for identifying opportunities, directions of development, and varying levels of influence when formulating regional economic and security policies. Taking these aspects into account, a decomposition system of macro-level economic security factors has been developed based on the nature of their impact.

The proposed classification of factors influencing the level of regional economic security can be used to form the necessary conditions for the safe and sustainable functioning and development of the regional economy, as well as to identify weaknesses in the existing mechanisms for ensuring economic security at the regional level. The concept of “conditions” also encompasses the entire environment in which the studied processes occur.

To ensure and develop economic security in a region, it is necessary to create specific conditions that provide real opportunities for its enhancement. Changes in production technologies represent one of the key conditions for elevating the level of regional economic security to a qualitatively new stage. This includes the production and acquisition of the latest high-tech equipment and technologies in the industrial sector, the transformation of research and education sectors, the availability of sufficient intellectual and financial resources, and a high level of innovative culture among the population, businesses, and government.

As noted above, such conditions may either contribute to or hinder the improvement of the region’s economic security. According to the Russian scholar S.A. Makin, if we take the generally accepted division

2 Source: compiled by the author.

of factors into external and internal ones, and supplement it with the criteria of their objective origin and the nature of their impact on economic security, we obtain a multifactor model that determines the level of regional economic security [5]. This model can be used to more precisely identify the aggregate conditions necessary for improving the level of economic security in a region.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Summarizing the study of factors influencing the level of regional economic security, it should be noted that many of these factors operate objectively, and their influence on the processes of ensuring and improving economic security is difficult to control directly.

However, through the implementation of state policy and the adoption of effective measures in the field of security, it is possible to stabilize or coordinate their impact using various management instruments.

The aggregate factors influencing the level of regional economic security form the basis for the development of strategies and programs aimed at its improvement.

The selection of specific measures and directions for ensuring regional economic security largely depends on the quality of analysis of the factors affecting it.

Regional public administration bodies should identify, take into account, and forecast the factors that have a significant impact on the economic security of the region.

List of used literature:

1. Мирзиёев Ш.М. "Янги Ўзбекистон Стратегияси". – Т.: Ўзбекистон нашриёти. 2021 й. - 464 б.
2. Берсенев, В.Л. Ведущие центры исследования проблем экономической безопасности в России / В.Л. Берсенев. // Экономика региона. - 2019. - Т. 15, вып. 1. - С. 29-42.
3. Кульман, А. Экономические механизмы / А. Кульман; пер. с фр. Е.П. Островской; общ. ред. Н.И. Хрустальной. - Москва: Прогресс: Универс, 1993. – С.17.
4. Сенчагов, В.К. Экономическая безопасность России: Общий курс: учебник / под ред. В.К. Сенчагова. - 3-е изд., перераб. и доп. - Москва: БИНОМ. Лаборатория знаний, 2016. - 97-113 с.
5. Макина, С.А. Анализ факторов, влияющих на инновационную активность российских предприятий / С.А. Макина, Е.Н. Максимова // Аудит и финансовый анализ. - 2010. - № 5. - С. 368-372.
6. Абулқосимов Х.П., Абулқосимов М.Х. Иқтисодий хавфсизлик: Назария ва амалиёт Дарслик.Т. 2019 й.-Б.455.
7. Турсунов Б.О. Иқтисодий хавфсизлик. Ўқув қўлланма.-Т.: "Инновацион ривожланиш нашриёт-матба уйи, 2021.-Б.15.
8. Экономическая безопасность регионов России: монография /С.Н. Митяков, Д.Н. Лапаев, Е.С. Митяков и др. - 3-е изд., перераб. и доп. - Нижний Новгород: Нижегородский государственный технический университет им. Р.Е. Алексеева, 2019. - 299 с.
9. Сенчагов, В.К. Экономическая безопасность России: Общий курс: учебник / под ред. В.К. Сенчагова. - 3-е изд., перераб. и доп. - Москва: БИНОМ. Лаборатория знаний, 2016. - 97-113 с. - Текст: непосредственный.

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